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STEMMING THE TIDE. OPPOSITION AND CONFLICT IN THE
CREATION OF NATURAL PROTECTED AREAS.
A CASE STUDY OF THE NATURAL PARK OF
PUEBLA DE SAN MIGUEL (VALENCIA), SPAIN

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The declaration of a new Protected Area is a decision made by political authorities which does not always gain the consensus of the people who live in the area concerned. In this article, we will look at the barriers in establishing a fruitful dialogue between both parties, taking as an example the Natural Park of Puebla de San Miguel in the province of Valencia (Spain). We will also explain the reasons for the opposition among the local residents to this new Protected Area.

Introduction

In recent years there has been a marked increase in efforts to protect that which had been left behind as a result of modern-day development, namely a 'lost nature'. This idea of the natural is marked by ambivalence; even though it may have originated in the post-industrial society itself, it is at the same time something we are constantly moving away from. This phenomenon of defining the limits of nature began, as is well known, in 1872 with Yellowstone National Park (NP) in the USA, and saw its beginnings in Spain with the declaration of the first NP in 1918.

Management over the environment was delegated to the regions at the beginning of the process of autonomy in Spain during the 1980s.¹ In this way Spain, which in 1975 had barely 150,000 acres of protected space (with a total of twenty-seven declared areas), increased its protected surface to over four million acres with more than five hundred Protected Areas (PAs)² in 2007 (Tolón and Lastra 2008).

The convening of the Earth Summit in Río de Janeiro in June 1992 was a huge boost for environmental policies. In particular, principle 4 of the Rio Summit which states: 'In order to achieve sustainable development, environmental protection shall constitute an integral part of the development process chain and cannot be considered in isolation from it'; set off the substantial development of Natural Parks in Spain (Santamarina Campos, 2008).

The declaration of a new PA has been, since the origin of NPs, a matter of dispute, confrontation and opposition between the regional authorities and the inhabitants of the area concerned. The interest in increasing the number of NPs in the Valencian Community led the autonomous government in 2007 to declare the most recent PA, the National Park of Puebla

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de San Miguel, in spite of local opposition. This study aims to analyze the causes and effects of the conflict, from a conservation perspective in order to take advantage of the lessons learned and propose other approaches to similar situations.

State of the Art

As West *et al.* (2006) comment, from the very moment the mythical Yellowstone Park was constituted (1872), the indigenous communities which lived there were evicted, with the help of the army. From the very beginning, the decision to declare an area a PA or a NP was made by the urban elite interested in reproducing a romantic state of 'wilderness', a return to a lost paradise. Such decisions tended to be made without taking into account what we would later discover, that every territory is shaped and modelled, in some way or other, by human beings. This same dispute occurred in the Yosemite NP, created in 1890, between those who promoted sustainable growth in the rural communities, headed by Mary Austin, and those who wanted to evict those who lived off the land, in this case shepherds and their flocks, headed by John Muir who, with his policy of 'wilderness', won the battle (Lebaudy 2013). Since then local communities, especially those in developing countries have started to be considered as an obstacle to the protection of sustainable growth. Since the nineteenth century there has been conflict between the defence of nature, promoted by governments and environmental associations, and the preservation of the rights of use and exploitation of natural resources, promoted by the local communities who abruptly found themselves amidst a globalised notion of environmental protection.

This conflict has been extensively studied in South America, Asia, Africa and Oceania. In particular, scholars have tended to focus their attention on indigenous communities, 'a common problem in developing countries' (Maikhuri *et al.* 2000). Naughton-Treves *et al.* (2005: 243) highlighted the ways in which local indigenous communities have helped maintain high levels of Biodiversity. One should not be surprised that it is precisely those same areas which end up being designated as new PAs.

The International Union for Conservation of Nature (IUCN) launched an initiative to enable conflict resolution in protected areas through ensuring that conservation practices respect the rights of indigenous peoples resulting in the Whakatane Mechanism (Freudenthal *et al.* 2012).

The management of PA's, however, is also a source of conflict between local communities and governmental authorities in Western countries. 'People may think that protected areas will restrict their leisure activities, such as camping and fishing, or limit their ability to use the land for agriculture, forestry, and hunting' (Stoll-Kleemann 2001b: 38).

The declaration of a new PA means limiting and regulating the rights the traditional owners and users had enjoyed up until that time, for the benefit of environmental protection. 'Park rules limiting access to resources create conditions of relative scarcity and uncertainty about future access.' (Koch 1998: 387). The opposition to the declaration of a new PA is a phenomenon which is also characteristic of developed countries.

These controversial issues have been analysed in the USA (Stern 2008; Gray 2004). In Australia, apart from the conflicts with the indigenous communities, Slattery (2002) analysed the public protests in opposition to the development of new services within the park in the Wilson Promontory NP.

We do not agree with West *et al.* (2006: 258) when they point out that 'The lack of

European regions in the literature demonstrates the relative lack of hardship created by protected areas on this continent'. There is an abundant literature that documents such conflicts in languages other than English, as highlighted by Ruschkowsk and Mayer (2011: 151). We can also find examples of this confrontation in several cases from Germany, Romania, Greece and Spain (Stoll-Kleemann, 2001b; Vasile, 2008; Theodossopoulos, 1997; Vidal-González, 2014). In France, the problems of management between livestock owners who traditionally made use of the pastures within the NPs and the administrators of the parks are indeed serious, as for example in the case of the Mercantour and Cevennes PAs.³ The recent reappearance of wolves in these areas has once again led to controversial confrontation between conservationists and livestock owners.

Opposition and Conflict in the Face of the Declaration of La Puebla de San Miguel as a Natural Park

Research methodology

The data for this study is the result of anthropological fieldwork carried out in the village of La Puebla de San Miguel, in the province of Valencia (Spain). While this village has 77 registered inhabitants, during the period in which fieldwork was conducted in the summer of 2013, there was a stable population of 20 year-round residents. A total of 18 were interviewed. The aim of the fieldwork was to get to know the different points of view and perceptions of the conflict which had arisen during the process of creation and declaration of the municipality as a Natural Park. In order to access these people we used the 'snowball' technique, starting from a previous contact with several inhabitants as a result of earlier ethnographic work, who then put us in contact with the rest of the informants. The main method used in order to compile data was through ethnographic interviews accompanied by participant observation, as well as meetings with participants and officials from the Park and the municipality, informal conversations and different materials such as a virtual chat room used by the inhabitants and several press releases.

The Causes of the Conflict

La Puebla de San Miguel is a municipality in the interior of the Valencian Community, situated 122 kilometres from the capital, and at nearly two hours by car from the populated coast it is not easy to access. The municipality has a large area of 63.6 km², a low population density, 1.4 per km² with 77 registered inhabitants, only 20 of whom are permanent residents. A continental Mediterranean climate, with very low temperatures in winter, makes only very scarce cultivation possible. This would explain the strong migration process to the rich coastal area. In 1920 the village had 399 inhabitants, and since the 1950s the population has continued to decline to the 77 present-day inhabitants. By contrast, this means that it has managed to preserve a rich environmental heritage with large forested areas which have been subjected to a respectful exploitation by the villagers, carried out within parameters of environmental sustainability.

In the decade between 1997 and 2007, Spain in general, but especially the Valencian Community, experienced a building boom, which is very evident in the abundance of uncontrolled construction work. This rampant construction was seen principally along the Mediterranean Coast due to the attractive nature of Valencian beaches for people buying a

second residence, mainly foreign tourists. As a compensatory policy in light of this intense urban growth, the Valencian government intensified the creation of new PAs, leading to 7 new NPs during the 2005–2007 period. This was an effort to justify the imbalances on the coast, the wealthiest and most densely populated areas, thus ‘legitimizing destruction through protection’ (Santamarina Campos 2008: 39). In this way, the interior areas, which are poor and sparsely populated (Vidal-González 2014), were compensated by the creation of new environmental containers and recipients, new spaces theoretically protecting nature. While the average protected surface area in Spain is about 28% of the community territory, the Valencian Community has protected 45.95% of its territory, the second community with most PAs, only behind the Canary Islands (Europarc 2010).

The most recent of these PAs created in the Valencian region was the NP of la Puebla de San Miguel, in 2007, which during the phase prior to its declaration as a NP had brought the inhabitants into confrontation with one another and also with the regional administration.

The Conflict

From the regional administration’s perspective, the territory is part of the interior, that is to say, with an extreme climate and harsh subsistence conditions. Its low population density and very large extension of territory (5,300 communal acres and 1,000 private acres) made it the ideal candidate to considerably increase the percentage of protected territory. The proposal was also relevant because the NP was an administrative figure which fitted exactly within the space of a single municipality. The first communication was with the mayor, who quickly saw this initiative as a great opportunity to improve and bring about progress. This would place this small and remote hamlet on the administrative ‘map’. Conversations between both parties were initiated; however, the mayor, who governed the village by a system of open council, only informed his close circle of friends. The rest of the inhabitants found out through the press about the intentions of the administration regarding their territory.

Growing rumours in the face of the project to create a Park and the amount of false stories circulating about its implementation created considerable social alarm amongst the villagers. As one informant says:

‘It was not well explained from the very beginning.’⁴

There was a strong and effervescent opposition to the mayor and the Park project under the slogan ‘Park No!’ And the mayor was accused of being a self-seeking manipulator, as another informant told us:

‘He must have thought this was his private manor.’

This outcry was the vehicle leading to an alternative candidature for the municipal elections. Despite the fact that several informative meetings were held by the regional administration in previous months, indignation had already been fuelled amongst the villagers against the mayor and the project conducted by the regional administration, and the situation had become very tense. Several conveyed their views in the following ways:

‘They come from outside to manage what is ours.’

‘We didn’t want anybody to come here poking their noses into everything.’

'It was something which was imposed on us.'

'They restricted our freedom.'

'It was something which Valencia had decided.'

'They steamrolled us and trampled on us because we are not important.'

'The park took over everything.'

'Is our opinion really worth nothing?'⁵

'We have felt manipulated and our opinion has not been taken into account.'⁶

'It has been done without taking us into consideration.'⁷

'Things can't only be dealt with in an office.'

'Things can't be done in such a dictatorial way.'

The inhabitants opposing the NP hung banners on the balconies of their houses (fig. 1) and carried out several pot-banging protests through the village. The forceful opposition was motivated primarily by their frustration at being treated like nobodies, without the ability to share their opinions about such a fundamental issue that directly impacts their lives. For them, finding out about the NP on television was simply humiliating.

Fig. 1

The indignation traveled by word of mouth between close neighbors and was accompanied by a growing number of rumors and suspicions that contributed to the growing irritation. When those in opposition organized a protest, the mayor was surprised. This was something which had never happened before, and which made the mayor call the Civil Guard in order to break up the demonstration, which was regarded as illegal. At the same time, a registration process for new villagers was initiated at the town hall with a view to reversing the situation during the following elections. This was denounced by the mayor, who argued that these people were not habitual residents. Consequently, technicians of the National Institute for Statistics (INE) carried out an inspection in the village, resulting in twenty-four new registrations being declared legally null and void.⁸

Changes in the municipal population census are indeed significant, since it went from 65 inhabitants in 2006 to 107 in 2007, and back to 66 once the elections were over in 2008. These actions, carried out in a small population of the interior where everybody knows one another, provoked consternation amongst the villagers, who had never witnessed such a situation. This situation was not without its accompanying threats and verbal excesses from the neighbours, which all inhabitants complain about in a small and otherwise peaceful village.

'Everyone must fight in defence of La Puebla so that the Park is not created.'⁹

'The mayor of La Puebla has his days numbered and let him be prepared because we will be going after him and all of his mates...'¹⁰

'They should be strung up in the village square.'¹¹

In spite of opposition from most (75%–80%) of the inhabitants, the regional administration declared that the entire municipality was a NP two days before the municipal elections. The party which led the opposition to the NP won an overwhelming victory, and since then opposition to the park has been their most important leitmotiv.

There was a strong feeling of indignation and powerlessness due to the imposition which had been effected. And there was also serious misinformation about the consequences that the new state of protection would have. Rumours and fears between neighbours were rife because there was a lack of clear, transparent information about the consequences and implications of the Park. Together with these, there was also a huge mistrust of anything which came from outside.

‘It’s going to become a reserve and we are the Indians.’

‘They are going to take away from us the land of our fathers.’

‘They are going to take away our lands.’

‘They took away our homes.’

The above three comments by drawing explicit analogy with the situation of native americans express fears of expropriation likening themselves to colonised ethnic minorities in the United States. They express a feeling of a loss of home but also of tradition and history. Other comments expressed fears of not being able to sustain their lifestyles and livelihood.

‘They don’t allow us to go for walks in our surroundings.’

‘You can’t gather wood.’

‘They were not going to allow you to do whatever you wanted (with your own land).’

‘We will not be able to work with our beehives.’

‘They will not allow us to take our flocks to pasture’

Confronted by what most of the village considered an imposition against the wishes of the majority, the town council proposed an appeal against the decree of the declaration of NP in the courts. This appeal was turned down. Subsequently, an appeal was lodged before the Supreme Court. This second appeal was also rejected and put an end to any further legal action.

Consequences

Throughout this period of time, the villagers, including those who staunchly opposed the declaration, have not observed any restrictions or suffered prohibitions due to the protection of the PA. Local people as well as people from the county have been employed to work in the NP. There has been significant financial investment in the area and potentially more in the future. There has also been a significant increase in the number of visitors to the area, thanks to the attraction of the new figure of protection. This has not been a nuisance for the villagers. On the contrary, it has generated a moderate increase in their incomes, mainly in the hotel and catering sector. In this sense, the person who runs the only bar that serves food in the village told us that it was thanks to the NP and to the influx of visitors which it produces, that she is able to stay open.

In spite of the fact that six years have gone by since the declaration of the NP, with the PA now functioning, there is an enormous chasm and open wounds between many of the inhabitants and the Park managers. As far as the village people are concerned, the latter represent the regional authorities. For this reason, it is difficult for the Park to function in a normal way. Having cooperation between the local and regional administrations is needed in order to achieve the much desired sustainable development in the area. The lack of communication between the two administrations is notorious. Therefore, what should have been a well-managed Park, which is an important factor for development in the area, has in fact become an element of conflict, division and confrontation.

‘What really matters is that there is agitation, that money is spent on court cases, that lies are told ... shepherds pasture, farmers work their fields, hunters hunt, antennas have been installed, there will be jobs, there is no avalanche of people ... but, what people no longer remember is the lies that were told and how upset people really are.’¹²

‘If we carry on being angry then we are not going to get anywhere.’¹³

The fact is that a significant number of the inhabitants currently work in the NP. These new jobs have been of great importance for the sustainability of the village. The PA has attracted new investments and increased local wealth, but the atmosphere of distrust against Park authorities still exists.

Discussion

Wilderness with people

A proposal for the declaration of a new PA is always a political decision (Baird 2009: 234) made by the authorities. They wish to improve their environmental commitment by offering an image of being concerned about the sustainability of the territory, something which is appreciated by people at large, but ‘not in my back yard’. In this sense, we are dealing with a popular action which responds to a growing demand for new ‘natural’ spaces which will allow people to ‘consume something environmental’. This demand to consume nature comes from a demographic majority which originates from the urban elite and the population who have had to sacrifice their lives in the great cities in the interest of progress. In this regard, ‘The urban tourist is more interested in visiting wild forests and mountains than wheat or corn fields’ (Vaccaro and Beltrán 2010: 14). For this reason the national and regional authorities, well aware of these new requisites of city people, have to respond to these demands with new declarations and the protection of new spaces for citizen consumption. They must also preserve landscapes of special relevance and sense of identity. The struggle for the preservation of the environment has turned into another government obligation, as the government feels that it has to undertake this commitment. It is an impulse characteristic of globalization; bringing together global environmental interests and local ones (West *et al.* 2006: 265, Pfeffer *et al.* 2001: 382) affecting all citizens.

In this regard, the authorities have the obligation, in order to preserve the common good, to carry out these practices in the territory. Several authors argue about the need to impose criteria of protection beyond the interests of the local communities which are directly affected by these decisions. Berkes (2007: 15188) states, ‘I have suggested that solutions need to be imposed’. Similarly, Brockington indicates to us that ‘local support is not necessarily vital for the survival of protected areas. Conservation can be imposed despite local opposition’. Then

he concludes shortly after, that ‘human costs have to be paid to prevent the destruction of the environment’ (2004: 401, 424).

Stoll-Kleemann highlights the antagonism between the two main protagonists in the process of conservation. She points out that ‘agency officials regard nature conservation as a battle against local opposition for the survival of nature’, and so those who manage nature ‘think participation is a waste of time’ (2001b: 39, 40). Vasile points out that in the Romanian case for example, ‘State representatives believe that communities should not be consulted for establishing protected areas, because of exaggerated demands and of lack of communication skills’ (2008: 90).

Managing a new park without understanding that within its limits there are people who live there turns out to be an illusion. Managing it behind the backs of those who are involved can only end up in opposition and permanent conflict. As Redpath notes; ‘There is evidence that effective participation improves relationships, increases trust, and reduces conflict’ (Redpath *et al.* 2013: 102). The analysis of environmental problems should be as inclusive and exhaustive as the topic itself, considering more the cultural than physical or biological dimensions, (Milton 1999).

Dialogue on behalf of Nature

Protection of the environment is the responsibility of the administration in its pursuit to work for the common good. It would seem clear, then, that the creation of a new PA should be preceded by a phase of dialogue, cooperation and negotiation between the parties involved: the administration and the inhabitants, as well as other people who may be affected by the declaration. It should be made clear that the new figure of protection will necessarily bring along with it a set of restrictions to the traditional users of the space. The authorities introduce ‘values, norms, and obligations that constrain local practices in a variety of ways’ (Pfeffer *et al.* 2001: 385) and the locals may associate ‘nature conservation regulations with restrictions on personal (and sometimes property) rights’ (Stoll-Kleemann, 2001b: 37–38). As Calero Valverde (2012) points out, the inhabitants of a PA, may feel suspicion and distrust in the face of plans of the administration to boost tourism and leisure for outsiders.

To delimit a space for its conservation could be seen as a victory for those who live in the cities. Those who live in the cities are the ones who are mainly responsible for contamination, and who consequently see the need to take control of and expropriate that which is not theirs in order to offset construction, contamination and urban life in favour of nature, rural life and fresh air. In this sense, it would be necessary to make sure that the inhabitants of rural areas should not pay for the abuses of the urban world, a type of ‘toll’ so that others may enjoy what they have conserved throughout many generations. Clearly, it is necessary to avoid a feeling among rural communities of being excluded from the property, use and management of the protected areas (Ojeda-Rivera 1999); this exclusion, apart from being rigorously unfair, will provoke important management issues in the future. It is essential that the inhabitants have more influence in the decision making process. ‘Although it may seem counterintuitive that the foremost influences on the success of environmental policy could be social, conservation interventions are the product of human decision-making processes and require changes in human behaviour to succeed.’ (Mascia *et al.* 2003: 649).

The importance of the need for agreements has been pointed out by many authors (Elbersen and Prados 1999; Stoll-Kleemann 2001a; Cock and Fig 2002; Roigé and Estrada 2010) and

entails reaching compromises, as befits any type of negotiation. In this sense, we feel that it is paramount that the administrations concerned should make people aware that the declaration of a PA is good news for the inhabitants of the area and should start a dialogue phase that aims for a mutually acceptable outcome (Redpath *et al.* 2013: 105). First of all, because local people have the greatest interest in preserving a territory, which thanks to its sustainable exploitation has been able to reach us in the right conditions. Secondly, because the creation of a new PA should attract wealth; therefore, it should secure population since there will be a respectful tourism bringing people who are interested in enjoying this lost natural environment which they cannot find in urban areas. And also, because authorities will have to establish compensatory actions for the inhabitants of the new PA, as stated by Martínez García (1997) and Palomo *et al.* (2011). These elements of positive discrimination avoid greater burdens and inequalities and should help to balance out the levies which directly or indirectly have affected an area. As Siebert *et al.* indicate ‘financial compensation and incentives function as a necessary, though clearly not sufficient, condition in this process’ (2006: 334).

Nature and Politics

The delimitation of a new territory, however, also has political implications at a micro level, since it affects the balance between the inhabitants of the villages in question and the administration. The declaration of a new park also implies, in greater or lesser measure, the recruitment of new personnel, which is something which could always be seen as a strong element of power. The recruitment of guards, of the park director, as well as other auxiliary staff should also always be understood as a political instrument. It empowers whoever has been recruited and increases political control over the rural area in question. One of the potential dangers ‘lies on the distribution of power and on the lack of communication skills’ (Vasile 2008: 88). As Agrawal (2005) states, ‘a decentralized government-in-community’ will be a good solution for equilibrated environmental governance.

Accordingly, the configuration of a new protected territory establishes a new political environment (Vidal-González, 2014). It is a new judicial demarcation of territory (Vaccaro and Beltrán 2007; Santamarina Campos, 2009) with conflicting interests, which need to be handled in an appropriate and balanced manner in order not to break the fragile ‘status quo’ of the local communities.

In the case of La Puebla de San Miguel NP, the management of the new PA has substantially modified the political balance, not only of the village but also of the county. The present ruling party, which at the time of the declaration of the Park was in opposition, has gone from not presenting itself at the municipal elections to having two absolute majorities and positioning itself as a clear opposition force to the regional authority in the figure of the director of the NP.

Conclusions

A booming consumer society and the massive concentration of the population in urban areas have made people aware of the importance of conserving a much-coveted nature. It has created an awareness of the fragility of our planet and the need to preserve it for future generations. This has provoked an important increase in the demand for PAs, which has been responded to by the Spanish national and regional authorities.

The areas which have been the object of these figures of protection in the world of today are usually those that, for various reasons, have remained distant from, but not divorced from,

the processes of industrialisation and urbanisation. These processes are in fact the reason why they are currently attractive and eligible for conservation in their theoretical state of archaic beauty. However, these conservationist actions are provoking a perception of exclusion of the inhabitants, owners and users of these spaces, which have now been declared PAs. Their rights, their traditional habits and customs have been disrupted by political decisions made by others, generally somewhere far away from the area itself. These decisions greatly affect their inhabitants, and may even lead to the limitation or prohibition of traditional uses. There is a sense of differential treatment and also feelings of humiliation due to the arrogance of National or Regional administrations. The administration, shielded by a declaration for the protection of a common good, introduce prohibitions without, in most cases, establishing a real dialogue and a phase of consultation with the local people.

On the other hand, it seems evident that the inhabitants of these new PAs should have all the right to enjoy the comforts and progress of contemporary modern societies. For this reason, it is paramount to establish a good balance between policies of conservation, in our opinion necessary, and a distribution of wealth which does not forget those communities which are established on the fringes of society.

The creation of a new PA should not only be the start of limitations and prohibitions, but also the beginning of real sustainable development in the area. This makes the new figure of protection viable and allows the local communities to live with dignity in that space, which in some way or other, has been taken from them and become the property of humankind.

The conservation of the environment, of the territory and landscapes inherited from our ancestors should be the force behind development in these local communities. The inhabitants of these areas should feel fortunate, not only for the moral good that the preserving of the environment implies, but also because that conservation, which undeniably does bring with it sacrifices, is accompanied by corrective measures for the imbalances created. The creation of a PA should make it clear to the population that there exists the possibility of continuing to reside in the area, of the arrival of new jobs linked to the management of the park, and of tourism which is respectful with the environment. As Folke argues 'we must move away from a way of thinking in which conservation is pitted against development to a framework of conservation for development' (Folke 2006).

Measures of social responsibility are also necessary as a compensation for the affected populations, which must not feel that they have been punished, but rather benefit from these measures. Only in this way can the management of the PA make sense and be viable in the mid- and long-term.

In this sense, local participation and co-responsibility in the management are imperative measures. The administrations must endeavour to maintain a frank and open dialogue in order to involve the local communities, even though it may be easier for them to act directly without going into processes of consultation and consensus.

Without any participation, dialogue and consultation between the local population and politicians, new parks can be declared, but it will be very difficult to carry out sustainable management of the area. Without the support of the population, if the declaration of protection has been made behind their backs or in the face of direct opposition from the inhabitants of the area, we feel that a PA lacks legitimacy and viability in the mid- and long-term. For this reason, we should strengthen all the channels of effective dialogue, something which is generally forgotten in these processes of protection of environmental heritage.

Notes

1. After previous regime and as part of a regionalization process, an important part of the competences were transferred to the 17 regions and autonomous cities in Spain, including environmental issues with the reintroduction of Democracy.
2. National Parks were managed by the State and Natural Parks, Natural Reserves, Marine Protected Areas, Natural Monuments and Protected Landscapes were the other Protected Areas managed by the Autonomous Regions.
3. I would like to thank my colleagues Anne-Marie Brisebarre and Guillaume Lebaudy for all their help.
4. The names and some of the personal details of the informants who have collaborated in this work have been changed in order to preserve anonymity and confidentiality
5. Anonimus. 2007, May 25th. Still we don't like the Park (Web log post). Retrieved July 5 2014, from <http://www.foro-ciudad.com/valencia/puebla-de-san-miguel/mensaje-383525.html>
6. Comment in the newspaper Levante-EMV. 25/05/2007
7. Levante-EMV.01/08/2007
8. Las Provincias. 22/02/2007
9. Anonimus. 2006, November 1st. Natural Park (Web log post). Retrieved July 5 2014, from <http://www.foro-ciudad.com/valencia/puebla-de-san-miguel/mensaje-279133.html>
10. Anonimus. 2007, May 8th. Down Mister the Mayor and his Pot (Web log post). Retrieved July 5 2014, from <http://www.foro-ciudad.com/valencia/puebla-de-san-miguel/mensaje-364877.html>
11. Anonimus. 2008, January 28th. They should be strung in the village square. (Web log post). Retrieved July 5 2014, from <http://www.foro-ciudad.com/valencia/puebla-de-san-miguel/mensaje-661761.html>
12. Anonimus. 2009, May 2. The Park Brigade. (Web log post). Retrieved July 5 2014, from <http://www.foro-ciudad.com/valencia/puebla-de-san-miguel/mensaje-2171793.html>
13. Anonimus. 2009, May 2. The Park Brigade. (Web log post). Retrieved July 5 2014, from <http://www.foro-ciudad.com/valencia/puebla-de-san-miguel/mensaje-2171793.html>

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